

POETIC CHARACTERISTICS OF O'TKIR HOSHIMOV'S WORKS

Madaminova Nodira Farhod qizi

Tuproqqala'a District of Khorezm region Teacher of School No. 4.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7393335>

Abstract. *In this article, the lexical units used in the stories written by O'tkir Hashimov are examined and researched. Poetic features are analyzed.*

Key words: *Language, language, discourse, trope, expressiveness, unity, artistic aesthetics, poetics, poetic analysis, linguistic analysis, linguopoetic skill, linguistic analysis, artistic work, linguistic research.*

ПОЭТИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ ОТКИРА ХОШИМОВА

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматриваются и исследуются лексические единицы, используемые в рассказах Откира Гашимова. Анализируются поэтические особенности.*

Ключевые слова: *Язык, язык, дискурс, троп, выразительность, единство, художественная эстетика, поэтика, поэтический анализ, лингвистический анализ, лингвопоэтический навык, лингвистический анализ, художественное произведение, лингвистическое исследование.*

INTRODUCTION

The creative maturity of any writer depends, first of all, on his loyalty to national ideas and values and the ability to express them at a high level in terms of linguopoetic skill in his work. In Uzbek linguistics, the language of works of art, original and figurative meanings of words, methods of transfer of meaning, as well as the relationship between form and content of words, active and inactive layers, theoretical foundations of these phenomena are discussed. began to study seriously. With this in mind, the lexical units used in the stories written by O'tkir Hoshimov are examined and researched in this scientific work. Analyzing O'tkir Hoshimov's stories from a poetic point of view, determining the artist's skill in using the tools of artistic representation, as well as the rich possibilities of the Uzbek language, and thereby determining the place of the writer in the development of the Uzbek literary language, constitutes the original content of our scientific work today.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The content of our scientific work is as follows:

- Determining the relevance of studying O'tkir Hashimov's stories from a poetic point of view;
- Analysis of phonetic-phonographic features of O'tkir Hoshimov's stories in connection with linguopoetics;
- Show the methodological characteristics of segment and supersegment events;
- Morphological analysis of stories;
- Identifying and analyzing their syntactic features;
- Studying O'tkir Hashimov's stories from a lexical-semantic point of view;
- Paying attention to the arrangement of stable compounds in stories;
- Paying attention to the significance of the use of proverbs and expressions;
- Determining the place of stylistic use of poetic pictorial means in O'tkir Hashimov's stories;
- Observing the participation of syntactic figures in stories;

- Giving importance to the location of tropes in stories;
- Identifying peculiarities in the use of artistic image tools in O'tkir Hashimov's stories.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It can be created on the basis of expressive-emotional tropes, stylistic synonyms, some stylistically limited lexical layers and phraseologisms. The use of tropes creates new word combinations with a new meaning in artistic speech. It enriches the speech with a new idea expressed in a different way, creates a convenient opportunity to express or evaluate the speaker's reaction to a certain event. The transfer of word meanings to a new meaning using different methods is called tropes. Words or word combinations are transferred to a new meaning through various methods. Accordingly, there are various methods of tropes: metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, epithet, allegory, irony, exaggeration, litota. The use of tropes in artistic speech creates new word combinations. Together with creating an opportunity to express or evaluate the speaker's attitude to a certain event, they enrich the speech with a new idea in a special way. In addition to the methods of trope that we have listed above, there is also simile-expression that serves for imagery, emotionality, and expressiveness. The idea of simile is the basis in simile and in almost all forms of trope. However, a simile differs from a trope by one feature: although similes and tropes are based on the idea of simile, in trope types, the signs of simile are expressed briefly, and in the simile expression, these signs are fully expressed. In addition, tropes do not include language tools such as -like, new, as if, like. consists of: 1) a similar thing 2) a similar thing 3) a similar quality 4) language tools expressing similarity The expression of simile is realized in the text. Because some of the poets and writers compare one object or event to another object or event, while another writer or poet compares that object or event to another object or event. Sometimes you suddenly wake up when you are lying on a platform or a cot in the middle of the yard on a milky moon night. ("Long nights" 43-b). In the sources, the tools that create similes are divided into two groups: lexical tools and grammatical tools. We can add the following to the lexical tools: like, like, like, news, like, like, like, similar, like, exactly, as if, equal, like, remind, just like. Additions such as -day, -dek, -dayin, -namo, -simon, -ona, -omuz, -cha, -larcha, -chalik, -chasiga are grammatical tools. Hotam-khasis laughs for some reason. Wrinkles on the spoon-sized face will disappear in layers. (67-b) If we get acquainted with this story, the only son of the hero of the story went to the war and did not return. we can witness that Plagan released only one picture of his son in different forms for all his money. This is why the author made the hero's face look like a "spoon". Such a simile to the face of the father, who lived with his son's fantasy throughout his life, increased the impact of the story even more. Sometimes you suddenly wake up when you are lying on a platform or a cot in the middle of the yard on a milky moon night. ("Long Nights" 43-b) In this sentence, the fact that the night is as white as milk is compared to the light. That's all! His color is as white as gauze... His beard and mustache have grown... (p. 65) - There you are! - he said in a childish cheerful tone. Hilola pressed her palm against the cold iron fence and looked at the water in surprise. "Look, look, you are floating," said Marat, pointing to the thin moon floating on the surface of the water. - That's you! Hilola felt warm feelings in her heart and looked at Marat lovingly. Now he was not as thoughtful and restrained as before, he was as simple as a child. ("Long Nights" 36-b) In O'tkir Hashimov's stories, similes are formed through lexical tools such as like, exactly, line, and grammatical tools such as -dek, -day, -chalik, -cha.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, speaking about Uzbek writers, manifestations of our national literature, it is natural that working people, their hard and responsible work, who are an integral part of our people's spirituality, National thinking, if necessary, preserve and develop our native language, literature with a rich history and Ancient Traditions, will pass before our eyes. In fact, the favorite of the Uzbek people, O'tkir Hoshimov, was also the most beloved child of the Uzbek people. All his works, stories, short stories have become the favorite works of the people. The study of the language features of the works of O'tkir Hoshimov began very early, when he now took a pen into his hands. We also drew on the analysis of only the stories of the writer as a continuation of such good deeds and analyzed their linguistic, poetic features. In the process of analyzing the stories, we saw how unique the writer's language was, how skillfully he used any means of the language, when showing the character, language of each hero, he was approached with his own individuality, not repeating each other.

In the stories of the writer O'tkir Hoshimov, emotional-expressiveness was high, and this circumstance served to ensure that the writer's works were manifested in an interesting, vivid way for the reader. In the writer's stories, which are a product of creativity, one can see the proper use of language units. Speech sounds, like other language units, have a role in generating expressiveness, being able to show that several meanings can be expressed through them. The expression of stable combinations in stories also ensured that the stories were richer in content, and the language of the stories became more folk. An attempt was made to reveal the peculiarities of both phrases and proverbs in stories. Syntactic forms and tropes' involvement in stories served to increase their artistic value. When drawing a literary text into linguopoietic analysis, logical concepts are illuminated, which consist of analogy, interjection on the basis of almost all of the pictorial means of the so-called migrations, which is a sign of how high the value of the work, the skill of the creator.

REFERENCES

1. Karimov S. Artistic style and means of expression image of language. Samarkand, 1994. 57-b.
2. Ne ' matov H., Rasulov R. Fundamentals of system lexicology of the Uzbek language. Tashkent, "teacher", 1995. – 128.b.
3. Rikhsiyeva G. Reflections on the basics of linguopoietic research // Uzbek language and literature. 2003, Issue 2. - Pages 84-86.
4. Saidkhanov M. Literary text as a communicative tool // Uzbek language and literature, 2009. No. 5, - pp. 77-80
5. Yerbayev B., Bogorov R., Lapasov J. Linguistic analysis of artistic texturing.- T., 1990. – B. 34.
6. Yuldashev M. The foundations of the literary text and its linguopoietic analysis. Tashkent, "Science" 2007, page 123